

The effectiveness of conditional dismissal in the treatment process in Greece: The case of KETHEA EN DRASEI

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Law 4139 of 2013, as amended, represents one of the most therapeutic oriented legislative efforts in Greece concerning drug offences and substance dependence. Among its provisions is the use of a restrictive condition known as conditional dismissal, which allows individuals facing criminal charges or serving sentences to undergo addiction treatment as an alternative to incarceration. This research examines the effectiveness of this legal mechanism by comparing the treatment progress of individuals who entered the KETHEA EN DRASEI Therapeutic Programme under a restrictive condition with those who enrolled voluntarily, without judicial involvement. The study focuses on 515 cases of individuals who participated in the main treatment phase at the Welcoming Released Centre between 2006 and 2017. These cases were categorised into two groups: those who attended the programme as part of a court-imposed condition and those who entered without such legal obligations. The analysis evaluates outcomes such as treatment completion and dropout rates in order to determine whether conditional dismissal enhances engagement and retention in therapeutic settings. The findings show that those entering treatment under a restrictive condition were more likely to complete the programme than those who joined voluntarily. This suggests that legal incentives may play a supportive role in promoting rehabilitation. The research also considers wider implications for criminal justice policy, particularly in relation to how the Greek legal system is shifting from punitive measures toward therapeutic responses for drug-related offences. By assessing the practical application of conditional dismissal within a structured treatment setting, the study provides valuable insight into the interaction between law and addiction recovery. It further highlights the importance of sustained policy evaluation to strengthen reintegration pathways and reduce the risk of relapse.

Keywords: addiction recovery; conditional release; criminal justice; drug dependence; Greece; rehabilitation; treatment outcomes

Substance dependence and drug-related offences remain a persistent challenge within the Greek criminal justice system (Karakasi et al., 2021), contributing significantly to prison overcrowding and social marginalisation. In response, legislative efforts such as Law 4139 of 2013 have sought to address drug use not solely as a criminal matter but as a complex health and social issue requiring therapeutic intervention. Among the law's provisions is the mechanism of conditional dismissal, which allows individuals to attend addiction treatment programmes as an alternative to incarceration. This represents a notable shift from punitive sentencing towards rehabilitation-oriented measures.

Despite this progressive framework, limited empirical research has examined the effectiveness of conditional dismissal in influencing treatment outcomes within structured therapeutic settings. Little is known about whether judicially imposed treatment conditions positively affect a person's likelihood of completing a rehabilitation programme or whether voluntary engagement yields better results. This gap is especially significant in the Greek context, where systematic evaluations of alternative sentencing and drug treatment integration remain scarce.

The aim of this study is to examine whether the imposition of a restrictive judicial condition, specifically participation in the KETHEA EN DRASEI Therapeutic Programme, enhances the likelihood of treatment completion. By comparing individuals who entered the programme under a court-imposed condition with those who enrolled voluntarily, the study investigates the motivational and behavioural implications of legal intervention in addiction recovery. The central research question is as follows: *How does the imposition of dismissal conditions affect the length of stay and completion outcomes of individuals in the KETHEA EN DRASEI Therapeutic Programme?*

Legal and therapeutic framework

Law 4139 of 2013 introduced a significant policy shift in Greece's approach to substance dependence by framing drug use as a complex biopsychosocial issue rather than a purely criminal act (Law 4139/2013). The law outlines provisions for addicted offenders to enter recognised treatment programmes in place of serving prison sentences. This change reflects a growing recognition that many drug-related behaviours stem from early traumatic experiences and long-term psychosocial disadvantage (Katsaounos, 2018).

One of the most significant features of the law is the introduction of conditional dismissal. This mechanism enables the judicial system to suspend criminal proceedings or prison terms if the individual agrees to attend a therapeutic programme. The treatment period is counted as part of the sentence, and in some cases, may lead to sentence reduction (Katsavos, 2010). Conditional dismissal can be applied at several stages of the legal process, including during pre-trial investigation, after conviction, or as part of release procedures under Article 105 of the Penal Code (Explanatory Report, 2013).

The effectiveness of this legislative measure depends heavily on the therapeutic infrastructure in place. Programmes such as those offered by KETHEA EN DRASEI are central to the law's implementation (Kethea, 2024). These programmes offer structured, community-based treatment focused on personal rehabilitation rather than punishment. According to the law, programme staff are required to submit regular progress reports to the judicial authorities. If participation is discontinued, the responsible prosecutor must be notified immediately, and the court may revoke the dismissal.

By offering a pathway to treatment rather than imprisonment, Law 4139 of 2013 signals a broader shift in Greek criminal justice policy. It aligns with international best practices, acknowledging that rehabilitation and social reintegration are more effective long-term solutions than punitive measures alone (Kruithof et al., 2016).

International models and comparative experience

Across many jurisdictions, alternative sentencing measures that prioritise rehabilitation over incarceration have shown promising outcomes for individuals with substance dependence (Belenko, 1999; Gottfredson et al., 2003; Relajo-Howell et al., 2024). International experience suggests that when treatment replaces punishment, rates of recidivism decline, and long-term recovery becomes more attainable.

In the United States, drug treatment courts serve as a model where eligible offenders participate in structured rehabilitation instead of receiving custodial sentences. Studies have consistently demonstrated that participants in these courts are significantly less likely to reoffend than those who do not receive treatment (Webster, 2015). Similar approaches have been implemented in other countries, including Germany, the Netherlands, and Poland, where probation services and therapeutic programmes are integrated into sentencing frameworks (De Kok et al., 2020; Jehle, 2015; Krajewski & Wodowski, 2015). These interventions have not only led to reduced offending but also improved social reintegration outcomes.

A comprehensive study covering all 28 member states of the European Union found that each country offers some form of alternative to incarceration for individuals with addiction-related offences (Kruithof et al., 2016). In most cases, treatment programmes are either embedded within the prison system or offered as part of the early release or parole process. However, barriers such as insufficient funding, inconsistent implementation, and legal limitations continue to restrict access to these alternatives.

The time invested in structured treatment has been positively linked with a reduction in criminal behaviour (Oliver et al., 2010). However, not all programmes yield the same level of success. Research also points to limitations, including partial treatment compliance and continued risk of reoffending. These findings highlight the importance of both the quality of therapeutic intervention and the legal framework that supports it.

In comparison to these international models, the Greek system was relatively slow to adopt non-custodial measures. Nevertheless, the introduction of conditional dismissal under Law 4139 has placed Greece in closer alignment with modern rehabilitative practices (Zacharaki, 2018). The current study aims to assess how effectively this legal provision functions when applied in real therapeutic settings.

The KETHEA EN DRASEI programme

KETHEA EN DRASEI is a therapeutic programme based in Athens that provides addiction treatment and social reintegration services to individuals involved with the criminal justice system (Kethea, 2024). The programme supports both incarcerated individuals and those who have been released, offering a community-based approach to rehabilitation. Its operations include treatment services at the Korydallos I and II Detention Centres, the Agios Pavlos Prison Hospital, the Elonas Thebes Women's Prison, and facilities in Livadeia. Beyond the prison system, the programme also runs a Reception Centre and a Social Reintegration Centre in central Athens for individuals recently released from custody (Kethea, 2024).

All services are delivered externally and on a non-residential basis, though temporary accommodation is available for those without stable housing. The approach emphasises consistent contact with the broader community through education, vocational training, and psychosocial support. The aim is to foster the development of individual autonomy, responsibility, and reintegration into social, economic, and political life.

Since 2003, the programme has also included a Support Centre for Released Persons, responding to the specific challenges faced by individuals who are doubly stigmatised as both former prisoners and former drug users (Vidali, 2013). This service helps participants transition from institutional settings to community life by offering practical and emotional support throughout the reintegration process.

Individuals may enter the KETHEA EN DRASEI programme through several pathways. Some join voluntarily before, during, or after criminal proceedings. Others participate under restrictive judicial conditions (Law 4139/2013). These conditions may be imposed at various legal stages, including pre-

trial detention, trial sentencing, or parole. In such cases, attendance in the therapeutic programme is a formal requirement tied to the person's legal status, and non-compliance may lead to legal consequences (Explanatory Report, 2013). The current research compares outcomes between those who entered voluntarily and those mandated to attend under these legal conditions.

Purpose and research question

This study examines the effectiveness of conditional dismissal as a legal tool to support addiction rehabilitation (Law 4139/2013; Kruithof et al., 2016). It focuses on whether individuals who are required by court order to attend the KETHEA EN DRASEI Therapeutic Programme show higher completion rates than those who enter the programme voluntarily. The aim is to explore whether legal obligation enhances motivation and commitment to treatment, and whether such involvement contributes positively to long-term outcomes (Gottfredson et al., 2003). Although Law 4139 of 2013 introduced conditional dismissal as an alternative to incarceration for drug-related offences, there remains limited empirical evidence on how this measure performs in practice (Explanatory Report, 2013). In Greece, few studies have systematically evaluated the differences in treatment engagement between voluntary participants and those under judicial instruction (Katsaounos, 2018). This research seeks to fill that gap by comparing the progression of both groups within the same therapeutic setting.

The results of this study may inform future developments in criminal justice and addiction policy. By identifying whether conditional participation influences treatment adherence, the findings can support more effective use of alternative sentencing (Weinrath et al., 2019). The research also offers insights that may help refine programme design and implementation within community-based recovery systems (Oliver et al., 2010). Therefore, the guiding question of this study is as follows: How does the imposition of dismissal conditions affect treatment retention and completion among individuals enrolled in the KETHEA EN DRASEI Therapeutic Programme?

METHODS

This study evaluates the effectiveness of conditional dismissal using primary data collected from the KETHEA EN DRASEI Therapeutic Programme (Kethea, 2024). The data consist of written and electronic records that trace the course of each participant from entry into the programme through to completion or disengagement.

In addition to internal documentation, the analysis includes relevant public records such as court terms and parole documents obtained from judicial authorities (Explanatory Report, 2013). These data sources allowed for an objective comparison between individuals who entered the programme voluntarily and those who participated under legal conditions.

The dataset includes 515 cases of individuals who attended the main treatment phase at the Welcoming Released Centre between 2006 and 2017. Among these, a subgroup of 120 individuals had been mandated to attend under a judicial condition. The remainder enrolled voluntarily. No researcher interference occurred during data collection. The records were provided by the relevant services upon request. Although some limitations may arise from how participant experiences were originally recorded, the researchers were not involved in that documentation process. Future research could complement these archival data with qualitative methods, such as interviews, to better capture the lived experience of conditional dismissal and its impact on treatment outcomes (Webster, 2015).

RESULTS

Between January 2006 and December 2017, a total of 120 individuals either attended therapeutic programmes while incarcerated and were subsequently released under judicial condition to participate in the KETHEA EN DRASEI programme or were referred to the programme with a court-imposed condition in lieu of incarceration (Kethea, 2024; see Table 1).

Table 1
 Annual outcomes for individuals with conditional dismissal (2006–2017)

Year	Total (n)	Graduated	Referred	Follow-up	Reintegration	Therapeutic Community	Interrupted	Did Not Show Up	Changed Plans
2006	1	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
2007	1	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
2008	4	4	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
2009	6	3	1	–	–	–	1	1	–
2010	13	9	1	–	–	–	3	–	–
2011	15	9	–	–	–	–	5	1	–
2012	25	11	–	–	–	–	13	1	–
2013	15	4	1	1	–	–	8	1	–
2014	13	–	2	1	–	–	8	2	–
2015	9	1	–	–	2	–	5	–	1
2016	12	–	3	–	2	–	4	1	2
2017	6	–	–	–	1	2	3	–	–
Total	120	43	8	2	5	2	50	7	3

Among these 120 individuals, outcomes varied significantly (Table 2). A total of 36% (43 individuals) completed the treatment process and graduated. Another 41% (50 individuals) discontinued their participation before completing the programme. A smaller proportion, 7% (8 individuals), were referred to other treatment services. Six percent (7 individuals) failed to appear at the programme despite being subject to a judicial order (Oliver et al., 2010). An additional 4% (5 individuals) were actively participating in the social reintegration phase at the time of data collection. Two percent (2 individuals) remained active in the main treatment phase, and another 2% (2 individuals) were in the follow-up phase. Finally, 2% (3 individuals) had their court condition transferred to a different programme before starting at KETHEA EN DRASEI.

For comparative purposes, Table 2 also presents data on the general population who entered the KETHEA EN DRASEI therapeutic community during the same period. In total, 515 individuals attended the main treatment phase. Among these, 21% (107 individuals) successfully graduated from the programme. Discontinuation rates reveal a notable contrast. While 70% (363 individuals) of the general population discontinued treatment, only 41% of those under a restrictive judicial condition did so, suggesting a possible association between judicial involvement and treatment retention (Gottfredson et al., 2003; Weinrath et al., 2019).

Table 2
 Conditional dismissals and general population

Outcome	Conditional Dismissals (n)	%	General Population (n)	%
People who graduated	43	36	107	21
Referred people	8	7	12	2
People who continue follow-up	2	2	15	3
People in reintegration	5	4	13	3
People in therapeutic community	2	2	13	3
People who interrupted	50	41	363	70
People who did not show up	7	6	–	–
People who changed plans	3	2	–	–

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study underscore the relevance of judicially imposed restrictive conditions as a mechanism for enhancing treatment engagement and retention among individuals with substance use histories (Weinrath et al., 2019). Participants who entered the KETHEA EN DRASEI programme under such conditions exhibited significantly lower dropout rates compared to their counterparts who joined voluntarily. This suggests that legal compulsion may play a facilitating role in maintaining commitment to treatment, particularly within the context of structured therapeutic programmes embedded in the criminal justice system (Belenko, 1999).

The data reveal a graduation rate of 36% for individuals under conditional release, compared to 21% among the general population. While the absolute graduation rate remains modest in both groups, the relative improvement associated with conditional dismissal indicates that the imposition of a legal mandate can positively influence outcomes. This is consistent with international findings, particularly those emerging from drug treatment court models in the United States and similar judicially supervised treatment frameworks in European contexts (Gottfredson et al., 2003; Webster, 2015). Prior literature has shown that structured legal incentives can reduce recidivism and support behavioural change, provided that treatment quality and continuity are maintained (Kruithof et al., 2016).

The present results also reinforce the notion that treatment retention is a critical predictor of successful outcomes (Oliver et al., 2010). Individuals under restrictive conditions were less likely to discontinue the programme prematurely, with a dropout rate of 41%, compared to 70% in the voluntary group. This substantial difference implies that the presence of a legal obligation may act as a stabilising force during the often-challenging early stages of treatment. However, it is also possible that the external motivation provided by judicial oversight contributes to better adherence without necessarily reflecting intrinsic readiness for change. This distinction has important implications for long-term recovery, especially post-programme reintegration. An additional strength of the KETHEA EN DRASEI model lies in its integrated approach, spanning from prison-based therapeutic communities to social reintegration centres (Kethea, 2024). This continuity of care may partially explain the relatively positive outcomes among participants with conditional dismissal, as it reduces fragmentation in service provision and offers consistent psychosocial support. Moreover, the structured collaboration between therapeutic personnel and judicial authorities appears to facilitate the implementation of conditional release as a viable sentencing alternative (Explanatory Report, 2013).

Despite the promising findings, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study relies on retrospective data from a single programme, which may limit the generalisability of results to other contexts or treatment models. Second, while the quantitative outcomes are clearly defined, the absence of qualitative data precludes a deeper understanding of participant experiences, motivations, or perceived barriers to treatment (Webster, 2015). Future research could benefit from incorporating interviews or longitudinal tracking to assess sustained recovery and social reintegration post-treatment. Additionally, selection bias may influence the interpretation of results. Individuals who accept or are assigned conditional dismissal may differ in unobserved ways from those who enter treatment voluntarily. Factors such as criminal history, psychosocial stability, or family support may

mediate treatment engagement and outcomes independently of the judicial condition. Controlling for these variables in future analyses could enhance the precision of the findings.

This study contributes to the evidence base supporting the therapeutic use of legal alternatives to incarceration for substance-involved offenders. The Greek legal framework, particularly Law 4139/2013, provides a progressive model for integrating public health and criminal justice responses to addiction (Law 4139/2013). The observed benefits of conditional dismissal in the context of KETHEA EN DRASEI reinforce the value of such initiatives and suggest that expansion and further institutional support for similar models could yield improved outcomes for both individuals and the wider justice system.

CONCLUSION

This study provides clear evidence that judicially imposed conditions of therapeutic participation can enhance treatment retention and completion rates among individuals with substance use histories. Participants who entered the KETHEA EN DRASEI programme under restrictive legal terms demonstrated significantly better outcomes than those who joined voluntarily. These findings support the view that structured legal engagement, when combined with a well-organised therapeutic model, can serve as a catalyst for recovery.

The data suggest that parole linked to treatment does more than enforce attendance. It may create a framework of accountability, support, and continuity that encourages personal commitment and psychological readiness. This approach reflects a more humane and pragmatic response to substance-related offences, shifting the focus from punishment to rehabilitation. The long-term collaboration between the judicial system and the KETHEA EN DRASEI programme highlights the importance of inter-institutional trust. It reinforces the notion that successful reintegration of substance-involved offenders is possible when legal and health systems work in tandem.

While dropout rates remain a concern, they must be interpreted in the context of addiction treatment as a process often marked by relapse and return. The study underscores the need for ongoing improvements in treatment provision, particularly in supporting individuals during the critical transition from incarceration to reintegration. The implementation of Law 4139/2013 represents a forward-looking legal framework that prioritises therapeutic intervention over punitive measures. Its practical impact, as shown in this study, offers a compelling case for expanding similar models of conditional treatment across Greece and beyond.

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